

Error propagation from AGIS downstreams

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Abstract

This document considers the propagation of errors (or more precisely uncertainties) from AGIS downstreams, for example to the Local Plane Coordinates. It summarizes the relevant formulae and provides some recipes for the calculations.

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1 Introduction

The astrometric core solution (AGIS) takes the astro elementaries (location estimates from the SM and AF observations) and converts them into estimated parameters for the sources, attitude, calibration, and global model. When considering any process that uses some or all of these data the question arises how to take into account the uncertainties of the various data. The computation and use of the Local Plane Coordinates (LPC; Lindegren & Bastian, GAIA-LL-061-3) is an example, where elementaries are transformed to the LPC system using attitude, calibration and global parameters from AGIS. Another example is the calculation of the field angles of a source in BP/RP or RVS for the purpose of the wavelength calibration, which uses a combination of source, attitude, and global parameters.

In this note we consider the uncertainties due to the following kinds of error:

1. Centroiding errors from the image parameter determination in IDT or IDU, $\sigma_{AL,obs}$
2. AL attitude errors due to the statistical uncertainty of the attitude determination in AGIS, $\sigma_{AL,astat}$
3. AL attitude modelling errors (due to the possible inadequacy of the spline representation), $\sigma_{AL,afit}$
4. AL calibration errors, $\sigma_{AL,cal}$
5. AL errors from the global parameters, $\sigma_{AL,glb}$
6. AL errors from the source parameters, $\sigma_{AL,src}$

Only the along-scan (AL) component of the errors is mentioned here, but there is of course a similar set of across-scan (AC) components, although most of them will be ignored in the following. For brevity, the subscript ‘AL’ will be dropped almost everywhere; thus, unless otherwise specified, ‘AL’ is always implied.

Not all of the errors listed above are relevant for a particular application. For example, the LPC of the image centroid do not depend on the source parameter errors, and the calculation of the field angles of a source at a given time does not depend on the centroiding errors¹ and is independent of the calibration errors. Although, strictly speaking, the different errors are not statistically independent (since the same data are used to estimate different parameters), the subset relevant for a particular application can always be treated as uncorrelated to a good approximation.² Thus, in the calculation of the LPC, the variance of the AL local coordinate w can be computed as

$$\sigma_w^2 = \sigma_{obs}^2 + \sigma_{astat}^2 + \sigma_{afit}^2 + \sigma_{cal}^2 + \sigma_{glb}^2, \quad (1)$$

¹Only indirectly via the attitude errors.

²The (small) correlation between source and attitude parameters is discussed in Holl & Lindegren (2012) and Holl et al. (2012).

TABLE 1: Order-of-magnitude estimates of the various kinds of uncertainties.

Uncertainty	Range [μas]	Remark
σ_{obs}	80–3000	AL in AF depending on G ; photon noise only (de Bruijne, JDB-053)
σ_{astat}	10–200	depending on star density and knot interval (Risque et al., 2012a)
σ_{afit}	10–1000	depending on thruster noise level and knot interval (Risque et al., 2012a)
σ_{cal}	0.1–100	guess – not further considered in this note
σ_{glb}	< 1	guess – not further considered in this note
σ_{src}	10–1000	depending on G and accumulated mission time

while the variance of the AL field angle η of a source, e.g., for the purpose of the geometric calibration of the RVS, can be computed as

$$\sigma_{\eta}^2 = \sigma_{\text{src}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{astat}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{afit}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{glb}}^2. \quad (2)$$

These formulae give the uncertainty of a *single* quantity such as w or η . However, when combining several different values of w or η , for example for the same source observed in successive CCDs, or different sources observed at the same time, it may be necessary to consider also the statistical correlations that arise from the fact that the computed values are partially based on the same parameters. An example is the LPC coordinates w of a given source in successive SM and AF observations, where the centroiding errors (item 1) and probably also the calibration errors (item 4) can be considered as uncorrelated among the different observations, while the attitude errors (items 2 and 3) are somewhat correlated and the global errors are strongly correlated. In order to perform the error propagation correctly when combining the different w values (e.g., in the object processing) it may be necessary to estimate these correlations and take them into account.

Naturally, some of the error sources are less important than others. Table 1 gives some order-of-magnitude estimates. The uncertainty due to calibration errors is very difficult to estimate, as it will depend critically on the model used. With the exception of gated observations of very bright stars it is probably negligible compared to the other uncertainties. The same goes for the global errors, if they are at all relevant in this context. In the following sections we consider in more detail each of the other kinds of error, and for the attitude errors we also discuss the correlations within a single field-of-view transit.

2 Notations

In the following we use, as far as practicable, the following notations:

Q the number of components in a quaternion ($Q = 4$)

M the order of the attitude spline ($M = 4$ for a cubic spline)

- N the number of elementaries in a FoV transit (usually $N = 9$)
- i, j indices of the elementaries within a FoV transit (from 0 to $N - 1$)
- k index of the FoV transits of a given source
- l index of the lag ($|i - j|$) in a FoV transit
- m the total number of observations in a least-squares problem
- n the total number of parameters in a least-squares problem
- ν the number of degrees of freedom

3 Centroiding errors

The uncertainty due to the centroiding error is formally given by the standard deviation of the AL location as estimated by the image parameter determination algorithm. In the table MDB/CU3/ID/AstroElementary it is given by `alCentroidError`.³ However, as discussed in Bastian & Lenhardt (BAS-037), this formal error should optionally be modified depending on the goodness-of-fit by means of the downweighting function $D(F, \nu)$ where $F = \chi^2/\nu$ is the goodness of fit (called *GoF* in Bastian & Lenhardt (BAS-037) and `gof` in the MDB) and ν is the number of degrees of freedom (`dof` in MDB). Thus,

$$\sigma_{\text{obs}} = \text{alCentroidError} \times D(F, \nu)^{-0.5}. \quad (3)$$

The recipe for computing $D(F, \nu)$ is detailed in Bastian & Lenhardt (BAS-037).

The centroiding errors of the different observations, even of the same source, are treated as uncorrelated. This should be accurate for the purely random part of the centroiding error, caused by photon noise and readout noise, but may not be completely true for the additional errors represented by a large goodness-of-fit F . For example, if the bad fit is caused by the source being a marginally resolved binary, the corresponding photocentric offset is likely to be the same in all the astroelementaries of a given FoV transit. However, this is not further considered here.

4 Statistical uncertainty of the attitude

The Gaia attitude, described as a function of time by the attitude quaternion $\mathbf{q}(t)$, is one of the main outputs of AGIS (Lindgren et al., 2012). The estimated attitude is given in the form of a knot sequence and the corresponding B-spline coefficients for each of the four components of the quaternion. This allows to compute $\mathbf{q}(t)$ for any t in a valid time interval. In this section

³Here, and in the rest of this section, `alCentroidError` is expressed in TDI periods, but the conversion to angular units is trivial using the nominal scan rate $\simeq 60 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$.

we describe the calculation of the formal uncertainty of this attitude, or more generally of any quantities (such as the field angles) which are computed by means of this attitude.

It should be noted that AGIS also estimates the *excess attitude noise*, which is something completely different from the statistical attitude uncertainty (σ_{astat}) that we are looking for here (it is rather related to σ_{afit}). The excess attitude noise $\epsilon_a(t)$, where the subscript a stands for either the along-scan component (AL) or the across-scan component in the preceding (ACP) or following field of view (ACF), was introduced to make allowance for attitude modelling errors, i.e., when the spline representation of $\mathbf{q}(t)$ is clearly inadequate because of a strong high-frequency component in the astrometric attitude.⁴ Including the excess attitude noise in (some of) the AGIS processes is particularly important for the identification of outliers in AGIS, where initial modelling errors otherwise could lead to the massive rejection of observations in ‘bad’ time intervals, thus preventing the attitude fit to be improved precisely where it is most needed. Normally, however, the excess attitude noise should be exactly zero, meaning that the attitude model (using splines) is statistically adequate. In Sect. 5 it will be discussed if and how the excess attitude noise should be included in the attitude uncertainty.

4.1 Propagation formulae

In AGIS the attitude is estimated in the form of the B-spline coefficients \mathbf{a}_κ , from which the attitude quaternion is computed according to Eq. (10) in Lindegren et al. (2012),

$$\mathbf{q}(t) = \left\langle \sum_{\kappa=\ell-M+1}^{\ell} \mathbf{a}_\kappa B_\kappa(t) \right\rangle, \quad (4)$$

where M is the order of the spline and ℓ the ‘left index’ of t in the knot sequence. Using a knot interval of (say) 10 s, the number of quaternion coefficients is ~ 16 million, representing a total of $n \simeq 64$ million attitude parameters (counting one for each component of the quaternion) forming the n -vector \mathbf{a} . Most generally, the uncertainty information concerning the attitude, under the assumption of Gaussian errors, is given by the covariance matrix of these numbers. Even taking into account that the attitude in practice is broken down into a number of separate segments, it is not practical to store, let alone compute, the complete covariance matrix for the attitude parameters. Fortunately, this is not required for a rigorous computation of the attitude uncertainty at an arbitrary time. What needs to be stored is just the Cholesky factor of the attitude normal equations.

If \mathbf{N} is the attitude normal matrix (of dimension $n \times n$), the Cholesky factorization calculates an upper-triangular matrix \mathbf{U} such that

$$\mathbf{N} = \mathbf{U}'\mathbf{U}. \quad (5)$$

Formally, the covariance of the attitude parameters is the inverse of the normal matrix, or

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{N}^{-1} = \mathbf{U}^{-1}(\mathbf{U}')^{-1}. \quad (6)$$

⁴Following Risquez et al. (2012a), the *astrometric* attitude is defined as the physical attitude averaged over the CCD exposure function for ungated AF observations.

While N and U are sparse (symmetric band-diagonal and upper-triangular band-diagonal, respectively), C is in general full. Storing U requires about QMn reals (or some 8 GB), which is clearly feasible, while C would require several orders of magnitude more. However, selected elements in C can be computed rather easily from U as they are needed.

More generally, let s be any scalar quantity (such as a field angle) depending on the attitude, for which we wish to compute the variance σ_s^2 due to the attitude uncertainty. With \mathbf{d} denoting the vector of partial derivatives of s with respect to the n attitude parameters, we have the linearised error propagation

$$\delta s = \mathbf{d}' \delta \mathbf{a}, \quad (7)$$

where $\delta \mathbf{a}$ is the vector of errors⁵ in the attitude parameters and δs the resulting error in s . Then

$$\sigma_s^2 \equiv E(\delta s' \delta s) = E(\mathbf{d}' \delta \mathbf{a} \delta \mathbf{a}' \mathbf{d}) = \mathbf{d}' \mathbf{C} \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}' (\mathbf{U}' \mathbf{U})^{-1} \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}' \mathbf{U}^{-1} (\mathbf{U}')^{-1} \mathbf{d}. \quad (8)$$

Introducing

$$\mathbf{h} = (\mathbf{U}')^{-1} \mathbf{d} \quad (9)$$

we finally have

$$\sigma_s^2 = \mathbf{h}' \mathbf{h}. \quad (10)$$

The above equations, while mathematically correct, tend to obscure the elegant simplicity of the actual calculations using the Cholesky algorithm. To explain how it is done in practice we outline below the main steps of the Cholesky algorithm as implemented in the `Normals` class.⁶

In order to solve the normal equations

$$\mathbf{N} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b} \quad (11)$$

the normal matrix and right-hand-side (rhs) are transformed by the successive application of the three algorithms C1 (implemented in the `reduceMatrix()` method), C2 (the `reduceRhs()` method), and C3 (the `solveRhs()` method); thus:

$$[\mathbf{N} \mid \mathbf{b}] \xrightarrow{\text{C1}} [\mathbf{U} \mid \mathbf{b}] \xrightarrow{\text{C2}} [\mathbf{U} \mid \mathbf{y}] \xrightarrow{\text{C3}} [\mathbf{U} \mid \mathbf{x}]. \quad (12)$$

(The method `reduceAndSolve()` performs the three steps in one go, but as we shall see it is extremely useful to be able to run each step separately.) What is done in C2 is to solve the triangular system $\mathbf{U}' \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{b}$ and put the result (\mathbf{y}) where the right-hand-side (\mathbf{b}) used to be. Thus C2 is mathematically equivalent to a pre-multiplication of \mathbf{b} by $(\mathbf{U}')^{-1}$, which is exactly what we need in Eq. (9).⁷

⁵Here, and in most other places in this note, ‘error’ strictly means the (signed) difference between the estimated and true quantity. The standard deviation of the error is called ‘uncertainty’ and denoted σ . We try to avoid using ‘error’ in the latter meaning although it cannot be completely avoided, as in the MDB field `alCentroidError`.

⁶See `GaiaTools/src/gaia/cul/tools/numeric/leastquares/Normals.java` and Appendix C in Lindegren et al. (2012).

⁷Similarly, C1 is mathematically equivalent to the pre-multiplication of \mathbf{N} by $(\mathbf{U}')^{-1}$, although the algorithm is quite different. Indeed, C2 (and C3) cannot be executed without first computing \mathbf{U} by means of C1. Finally, C3 solves the triangular system $\mathbf{U} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{y}$ and put the result (\mathbf{x}) where \mathbf{y} used to be.

Two important points should be made concerning the steps shown in Eq. (12). First, that C1 is the toughest part of the algorithm, as the required number of arithmetic operations scales as nb^2 , where $b = QM$ ($= 16$) is the bandwidth. C2 and C3 require (at most) of the order of nb operations.⁸ Second, each of the steps C1–C3 makes an in-place calculation, i.e., U replaces (the non-redundant upper-diagonal part of) N , y replaces b , and so on. It is useful to think of these steps as performing certain transformations of the matrix and right-hand-side, rather than as a calculator. The transformation done by C1 and C2 is called ‘reduce’ and is equivalent to a pre-multiplication by $(U')^{-1}$. The transformation done by C3 is called ‘solve’ and is equivalent to a pre-multiplication by U^{-1} .

The same principle as outlined above can be used to calculate the covariance between two arbitrary quantities s_1 and s_2 depending on the same attitude data. They could for example be the AL and AC components of the field angles of a source at a given time, or the AL components of the attitude at two different times. Let d_1 and d_2 be their partial derivative vectors, and let h_1 and h_2 be the reduced vectors (obtained by applying C2 to the partial derivative vectors). Then, in analogy with Eq. (8),

$$\text{Cov}(s_1, s_2) \equiv E(\delta s_1' \delta s_2) = d_1' C d_2 = h_1' h_2. \quad (13)$$

The correlation coefficient between s_1 and s_2 is

$$\rho_{12} = \frac{\text{Cov}(s_1, s_2)}{\sigma_{s_1} \sigma_{s_2}} = \frac{h_1' h_2}{\sqrt{(h_1' h_1)(h_2' h_2)}}. \quad (14)$$

4.2 Practical representation of attitude uncertainty

Although Sect. 4.1 formally solves the problem of propagating the attitude uncertainty into any quantity that is a function of the attitude (such as the field angles), it is not very convenient for most applications. The reason is that the matrix U , although manageable, is still huge and quite impractical to use. A more convenient method can be found by noting two important characteristics of the attitude uncertainties:

1. At any time the attitude errors AL, ACP and ACF are roughly uncorrelated.
2. The attitude errors are strongly correlated on time scales smaller than the knot interval, and progressively more de-correlated for separations greater than the knot interval.

The first property is a consequence of the way the attitude is determined from AL and AC measurements which are statistically independent, and the fact that the basic angle is not far from 90° . (Indeed, the expected correlations between the AL and the AC components are close to zero, while between ACP and ACF it is about $\cos \Gamma \simeq -0.284$ for basic angle $\Gamma = 106.5^\circ$.)

⁸‘At most’, because there could be ways to reduce this significantly; see Appendix B.

FIGURE 1: Autocorrelation functions of the along-scan attitude errors for different values of the attitude regularization parameter λ . From Holl et al. (2012).

The second property follows from the ‘local’ nature of the B-splines, making the fitted spline relatively insensitive to data more than a few knot intervals away. We can therefore infer that most of the information on the attitude uncertainty can be described by a discrete sampling of the three functions $\sigma_a(t)$, where a stands for AL, ACP, or ACF. The sample interval need not be much smaller than the knot interval.

In the case of a regular knot sequence with (constant) knot interval Δt and in the limit of a quasi-continuous, constant rate of observations, the autocorrelation function of the attitude errors has the shape shown in Fig. 1. It depends on the value of the regularization parameter λ used in the solution [see Eq. (81) in Lindegren et al. (2012)], but for the relatively small values ($\sim 10^{-2}$) normally used the correlation length is about $0.8\Delta t$. Thus $\sigma_a(t)$ probably needs to be sampled at roughly half the knot interval to allow accurate interpolation. Actually, for a completely different reason (Sect. 4.3), it may be convenient to use a sampling interval equal to the time between successive CCDs in the AF, namely 4.855 s.

Consequently, it is proposed that the practical specification of the statistical attitude uncertainty consists of discrete values of σ_{AL} , σ_{ACP} , and σ_{ACF} at points separated by approximately 4.855 s. For a 5 year mission this amounts to about 100 million reals in total, or less than 1 GB. Nevertheless, the reduced normal equations matrices \mathbf{U} for the different attitude segments should also be preserved, as they contain the complete attitude covariance information. A recipe for computing the attitude sigmas, as well as the mutual correlations among the AL, ACP, and ACF components, should they be needed, is given in Appendix A.

4.3 Attitude errors in a field-of-view transit

When considering the (up to) nine consecutive AL measurements together, it is no longer true that they can be regarded as statistically independent. While the centroiding errors (item 1) may be uncorrelated, at least in the absence of systematic errors due to LSF mismatch and CTI effects, the attitude errors in items 2 and 3 are certainly correlated. For the statistical errors (item 2) this is shown by Fig. 1.

The actual correlation between the AL attitude estimation errors at two different times t_1 and t_2 can be computed as described in Sect. 4.1. If the vector \mathbf{h} for the AL attitude is anyway computed at intervals of 4.855 s in order to estimate σ_{astat} at these points, it is a relatively small overhead to also compute the correlation coefficients ρ for time differences that are multiples of 4.855 s up to (say) $18 \times 4.855 \simeq 87$ s, which is more than the complete FoV transit from SM to RVS. Correlations over longer time spans will never be needed.

For a regular knot sequence the AL correlation coefficient ρ_{ij} between two elementaries i and j in the same FoV transit will, to a good approximation, be a function of $|i - j|$ only. Also for a realistic knot sequence it is possible that the correlations can be estimated, to sufficient precision, as a function of $|i - j|$, based on some sample correlations computed with the more rigorous method described above. Below we use ρ_l to denote the correlation coefficient for lag $l = |i - j|$.

Let $w_i, i = 0 \dots n - 1$ be the n (normally 9) consecutive AL local plane coordinates for a FoV transit, with standard uncertainties due to the statistical attitude errors

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{astat}} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{\text{stat},0} \\ \sigma_{\text{stat},1} \\ \vdots \\ \sigma_{\text{stat},n-1} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

Having estimated the correlation coefficients ρ_l as described above, the covariance matrix for the AF transit can now be constructed:

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{astat}} = \text{diag}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{astat}}] \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_1 & \rho_2 & \dots & \rho_{n-1} \\ \rho_1 & 1 & \rho_1 & \dots & \rho_{n-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{n-1} & \rho_{n-2} & \rho_{n-3} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \text{diag}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{astat}}]. \quad (16)$$

This matrix will be combined with the corresponding matrices for the other error sources to form the complete covariance matrix of the AL local plane coordinates.

5 Attitude uncertainty due to modelling errors

The attitude modelling error refers to the difference between the actual *astrometric*⁹ attitude of Gaia and the best-fitting attitude spline using the adopted knot sequence.¹⁰ The modelling errors are much harder to estimate than the random (statistical) errors discussed in Sect. 4, but one can get some handle on them in different ways, for example:

1. They can be estimated by means of detailed simulations of the attitude, including a number of known perturbations. The Gaia Dynamical Attitude Model (DAM; Risquez et al., 2012b) is the most realistic model available, and has been used by Risquez et al. (2012a) to estimate the modelling errors.
2. The excess attitude noise $\epsilon_a(t)$ determined as part of the AGIS solution (Sects. 3.6 and 5.2.5 in Lindegren et al., 2012) is a quantification of the modelling errors, although its precise relation to the modelling errors has not been explored.
3. Various statistical tests of the attitude residuals (AL, ACP and ACF) as functions of time (including spline fitting with a denser knot sequence than was used in the solution) should provide the most reliable characterization of these errors.
4. The AL attitude residuals for gated observations relative to the astrometric attitude provide an estimate of the power of high-frequency signals in the physical attitude, from which the modelling errors can be derived.

In the absence of real data only the first method is available. Risquez et al. (2012a) estimated the level of modelling errors as a function of the knot interval τ and found

$$\sigma_{\text{afit}} = A_{\text{afit}} \left(\frac{\tau}{10 \text{ s}} \right)^\alpha \quad (17)$$

with exponent $\alpha = 1.89 \pm 0.01$ and $A_{\text{afit}} \simeq 40 \mu\text{as}$ for nominal thruster noise. It should be noted, however, that these values were not taking into account the higher flexibility of the spline obtained in a three-axis attitude fit with small λ (see footnote 10). The modelling errors are of course correlated as a function of the time lag, but because of the very efficient high-pass filtering effected by the spline fit (cf. Fig. 1 in Lindegren, GAIA-LL-048) the correlation is expected to be very small for lags greater than a few knot intervals. In any case the correlation coefficient ρ_{afit} can be estimated from the DAM data as function of the lag. This, together with Eq. (17), can be used to construct the covariance matrix C_{afit} in complete analogy with Eq. (16).

⁹See footnote 4.

¹⁰‘Best fitting’ should be interpreted as referring to the three-axis attitude represented by the spline, rather than a separate spline fit to each of the four components of the quaternion (see Appednix D in Holl et al., 2012, for an explanation of the difference). The goodness-of-fit will depend on the regularization parameter λ as well as the knot sequence; cf. Fig. 1.

6 Propagation of uncertainties from the source parameters

This section only covers the propagation of uncertainties for non-solar system sources from the source parameters estimated in AGIS to the field coordinates (η, ζ) .

For every source processed by AGIS (as primary or secondary source) there is a (6×6) covariance matrix \mathbf{C}_{src} . (The MDB may store equivalent information from which this matrix can be reconstructed.)

Given the source parameters and attitude, the field angles (η, ζ) can be computed for an arbitrary time t using the coordinate transformation framework. This will also compute the partial derivative vectors

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{AL}} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial\eta/\partial\alpha^* \\ \partial\eta/\partial\delta \\ \partial\eta/\partial\varpi \\ \partial\eta/\partial\mu_{\alpha^*} \\ \partial\eta/\partial\mu_{\delta} \\ \partial\eta/\partial\mu_r \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{d}_{\text{AC}} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial\zeta/\partial\alpha^* \\ \partial\zeta/\partial\delta \\ \partial\zeta/\partial\varpi \\ \partial\zeta/\partial\mu_{\alpha^*} \\ \partial\zeta/\partial\mu_{\delta} \\ \partial\zeta/\partial\mu_r \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

from which

$$\sigma_{\text{AL,src}}^2 = \mathbf{d}'_{\text{AL}} \mathbf{C}_{\text{src}} \mathbf{d}_{\text{AL}}, \quad \sigma_{\text{AC,src}}^2 = \mathbf{d}'_{\text{AC}} \mathbf{C}_{\text{src}} \mathbf{d}_{\text{AC}}, \quad \rho_{\text{AL,AC,src}} = \frac{\mathbf{d}'_{\text{AL}} \mathbf{C}_{\text{src}} \mathbf{d}_{\text{AC}}}{\sigma_{\text{AL,src}} \sigma_{\text{AC,src}}}. \quad (19)$$

7 Synthesis

7.1 Addition of covariances

The covariance matrix for the sum of independent effects is obtained by summing the covariance matrices for the individual effects exactly as for the variances. Thus, the covariance of the AL local plane coordinates w_i in a FoV transit, when combining items 1–3 in Sect. 1, is obtained as

$$\mathbf{C}_w = \text{diag}[\sigma_{\text{obs},0}^2, \dots, \sigma_{\text{obs},n-1}^2] + \mathbf{C}_{\text{astat}} + \mathbf{C}_{\text{afit}}. \quad (20)$$

Here $\mathbf{w} = [w_0 \ w_1 \ \dots \ w_{n-1}]'$ is the vector of AL local plane coordinates. The first term is diagonal because the elementary errors are assumed to be uncorrelated (Sect. 3).

Successive FoV transits of the same source can always be treated as uncorrelated. The covariance matrix for the complete set of AL local plane coordinates of a given source is therefore block-diagonal, with matrices like Eq. (20) along the diagonal.

7.2 How important are the correlations?

Is it at all necessary to take into account the correlations represented by the off-diagonal elements in Eq. (3)? The answer depends, naturally, on the relative sizes of σ_{obs}^2 and $\sigma_{\text{astat}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{afit}}^2$ as well as on the absolute sizes of the correlation coefficients ρ_l that appear in Eq. (16) and the corresponding expression for C_{afit} . For faint stars σ_{obs}^2 will always be much larger than the attitude variance, and the error made by assuming uncorrelated data will be very small.

The size of the attitude correlation coefficients ρ_l will depend strongly on the knot interval used and, for the modelling errors, on the actual attitude perturbations. It could very well be that these correlations are quite small in the final AGIS solutions (using many primary sources and hence a short knot interval), in which case the off-diagonal elements in Eq. (20) could be neglected without much harm even for bright stars.

To take a specific if somewhat extreme example, let us assume that $\rho_l = 1$ for both the statistical and modelling errors, and a total attitude uncertainty of $30 \mu\text{as}$ (cf. Table 1). The astrolementaries of a bright source may have $\sigma_{\text{obs}} = 80 \mu\text{as}$. Now consider the mean AL location resulting from the combination of $n = 9$ elementaries. If the attitude correlations are neglected the computed standard deviation of the mean location will be $\sqrt{(80^2 + 30^2)/9} = 28.5 \mu\text{as}$, while that actual standard deviation is $\sqrt{80^2/9 + 30^2} = 40.1 \mu\text{as}$. The final astrometric, orbital, and other parameters derived for the source will have formal uncertainties that are underestimated by the same factor. However, the goodness-of-fit ($F = \chi^2/\nu$) obtained in the least-squares solution for this source could still be close to unity, because the uncertainty of the individual observations is correctly estimated! Such underestimation of the actual uncertainty, unrevealed by the usual GoF, is clearly very undesirable. We therefore conclude that it is, in general, necessary to take the correlations into account.

7.3 How to take the correlations rigorously into account

In this section we describe how the covariances among all the AL data of a given source can be rigorously taken into account in a single least-squares solution for the source parameters (where the source model can be arbitrarily complex). In the next section we propose a scheme for compressing these data to a single AL coordinate per FoV transit. Since it is possible to demonstrate, under some reasonable assumptions, that the compressed data leads to exactly the same solution as the full data, we can conclude that the compression in principle entails no loss of information.

Let

$$Ax \simeq w \tag{21}$$

be the design equations for the full (linearised) problem. It is written here in terms of the AL local plane coordinates w , but the results in this section are completely general. The design matrix A has the dimensions $m \times n$, where m is the total number of observations (elemen-

taries) and n is the number of unknowns (parameters to be estimated in the source model). The covariance of the data vector \mathbf{w} is given by the positive-definite matrix \mathbf{C} of dimension $m \times m$ (it would typically have the block-diagonal structure mentioned in Sect. 7.1). That is, with $\delta\mathbf{w}$ denoting the errors in \mathbf{w} we have

$$\mathbb{E}(\delta\mathbf{w} \delta\mathbf{w}') = \mathbf{C}. \quad (22)$$

Now let \mathbf{U} be the Cholesky factor of the covariance matrix, such that $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{U}'\mathbf{U}$. (For a block-diagonal covariance matrix the Cholesky factorization can be made one block at a time.) The weight-normalized design equations are

$$(\mathbf{U}')^{-1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \simeq (\mathbf{U}')^{-1}\mathbf{w} \quad \text{or} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x} \simeq \tilde{\mathbf{w}}, \quad (23)$$

where the tilde (\sim) signifies pre-multiplication by $(\mathbf{U}')^{-1}$. (We note that both the Cholesky factorization of \mathbf{C} and the subsequent transformations of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{w} can be done by means of the `Normals` class as described in Sect. 4.1.) The weight-normalization means that the errors in the transformed data $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}$ are uncorrelated and have unit variance, as is easily shown:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}} \delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}') &= \mathbb{E}[(\mathbf{U}')^{-1}\delta\mathbf{w} \delta\mathbf{w}'(\mathbf{U})^{-1}] \\ &= (\mathbf{U}')^{-1}\mathbb{E}(\delta\mathbf{w} \delta\mathbf{w}')(\mathbf{U})^{-1} \\ &= (\mathbf{U}')^{-1}\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{U})^{-1} \\ &= (\mathbf{U}')^{-1}\mathbf{U}'\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{U})^{-1} \\ &= \mathbf{I}. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The transformed design equations $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x} \simeq \tilde{\mathbf{w}}$ can now be treated with any standard least-squares method, including orthogonalization methods such as the use of Householder transformations. For example, if normal equations are used we have to solve the system

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}'\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}'\tilde{\mathbf{w}}, \quad (25)$$

and the formal covariance of the least-squares estimate is given by $(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}'\tilde{\mathbf{A}})^{-1}$. With $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ denoting the least-squares estimate, the normalized residuals are given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{r}} = \tilde{\mathbf{w}} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \quad (26)$$

and $\chi^2 = \tilde{\mathbf{r}}'\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ should follow the chi-square distribution with $\nu = m - n$ degrees of freedom. However, the individual normalized residuals cannot easily be interpreted (e.g., when looking for outliers), so it is probably better to compute first the non-normalized residuals $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and do the transformation to $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ afterwards in order to compute χ^2 .

7.4 Compression: One data point per FoV transit

If the LPC are to be given as one point per FoV crossing, then the corresponding set of data need to be compressed to a single ‘effective’ AL coordinate FoV crossing.¹¹ Formally, the

¹¹This actually corresponds to the ‘normal place’ discussed in Lindegren (LL-076).

compression is achieved as a weighted mean of the data, taking into account the correlations by means of the covariance matrix. If the full data set in Eq. (25) is broken down into the FoV transits k , the normal equations can be written

$$\left(\sum_k \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k' \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k \right) \mathbf{x} = \sum_k \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k' \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k, \quad (27)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k$ stand for the transformed coordinates i and design matrix for transit k . We assume that each FoV transit consists of N (usually 9) elementaries.

The above equations can be compressed to a single data point per FoV transit, provided that the rows in the original design matrix \mathbf{A}_k are nearly the same. Recalling that each row contains the partial derivative of one AL coordinate w with respect to the source parameters, and that these derivatives are nearly the same for all the elementaries in a FoV transit, we can write, to a good approximation,

$$\mathbf{A}_k = \mathbf{1} \mathbf{a}'_k, \quad (28)$$

where \mathbf{a}_k is the column vector of the partial derivatives of w with respect to the source parameters, and $\mathbf{1}$ is a column vector of length N containing ones. With this (very good) approximation we have

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k = (\mathbf{U}'_k)^{-1} \mathbf{1} \mathbf{a}'_k, \quad (29)$$

and consequently

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k' \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k = \mathbf{a}_k \mathbf{1}' (\mathbf{U}_k)^{-1} (\mathbf{U}'_k)^{-1} \mathbf{1} \mathbf{a}'_k = \mathbf{a}_k \mathbf{1}' \mathbf{P}_k \mathbf{1} \mathbf{a}'_k \quad (30)$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k' \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k = \mathbf{a}_k \mathbf{1}' (\mathbf{U}_k)^{-1} (\mathbf{U}'_k)^{-1} \mathbf{w}_k = \mathbf{a}_k \mathbf{1}' \mathbf{P}_k \mathbf{w}'_k, \quad (31)$$

where

$$\mathbf{P}_k = \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \quad (32)$$

is the weight matrix for the FoV transit, i.e., the inverse of Eq. (20).

In Eq. (31) we have $\mathbf{1}' \mathbf{P}_k$, which is a row vector of length N containing the sums of the N columns in \mathbf{P}_k . If these sums are called P_i , $i = 0, \dots, N-1$ and similarly the elements in \mathbf{w}_k are denoted w_i we thus have

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k' \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_k = \mathbf{a}_k \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i w_i. \quad (33)$$

In Eq. (30) we have $\mathbf{1}' \mathbf{P}_k \mathbf{1}$, which equals $\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i$. Thus,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k' \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_k = \mathbf{a}_k \mathbf{a}'_k \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i. \quad (34)$$

If the N data points in \mathbf{w}_k , with weight matrix \mathbf{P}_k , are replaced by the single data point

$$\bar{w}_k = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i w_i}{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i} \quad (35)$$

with weight $\sigma_k^{-2} = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i$, it is seen that the normal equations constructed from these (compressed) data will be exactly the same as for the original data set. This will hold for any partial derivative vectors \mathbf{a}_k , as long as they are practically the same within a FoV transit. Equation (35) shows that the normal place for a FoV transit should be computed as the weighted mean of the individual data points, using weights (P_i) that are the sums of the columns (or rows) in \mathbf{P}_k , and it should be assigned the standard deviation

$$\sigma_k = \left(\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i \right)^{-1/2}. \quad (36)$$

Before computing the weighted mean as described above, the individual data points should be scrutinized for outliers. Because the astrometric model (i.e., the design matrix \mathbf{A}) is not known at the time when outliers have to be identified, the only way to identify outliers is to look at the concordance among the N values w_i in a single FoV transit.¹²

The procedure for outlier rejection could be as follows. First compute \bar{w}_k as the weighted mean of all N values and the corresponding standard deviation σ_k . Then compute, for each i , the deviation $\Delta_i = w_i - \bar{w}_k$ and its formal standard deviation σ_i . The latter can be rigorously computed from the known covariance \mathbf{C}_k of the N values, and is found to be

$$\sigma_i^2 = [\mathbf{C}_k]_{ii} - \sigma_k^2. \quad (37)$$

Finally reject the point with the largest normalized deviation, $|\Delta_i/\sigma_i|$, if it exceeds a certain value κ (~ 3). If a rejection is made it is necessary to recompute the weight matrix (after deleting the corresponding row and column in \mathbf{C}) and the weights, and repeat the process.

The above procedure could be combined with an estimate of the goodness-of-fit $F = \chi^2/\nu$ among the $N - 1$ remaining points when considering whether a certain point is an outlier. This value of F , together with ν , can be used to empirically increase σ_i in a similar way as in Sect. 3. This would possibly make the outlier rejection more robust, but it would also reduce the power of finding more than one outlier in a FoV transit.

The problem at hand can be described very generally as that of finding the best estimate of a scalar quantity w , and the uncertainty of this estimate, given N measurements with a (formal) covariance \mathbf{C} . The solution must take into account that there could be outliers as well as the possibility that \mathbf{C} has been underestimated.

¹²Under the assumption of Eq. (28), the values w_i in a single transit can only differ due to the noise.

A Appendix: A recipe for computing σ_a

```

// the attitude data is contained in the gaia.cul.tools.satellite.attitude.fitting.Spline object
Spline spline = new Spline(...);

// get the knot sequence, number of unknowns, bandwidth of the normals, etc
KnotSequence ks = spline.getKnotSequence();
int splineOrder = ks.getSplineOrderM();
int nUnknowns = Quaternion.NUM_COMP * ks.getNDegsFreedomN();
int width = Quaternion.NUM_COMP * ks.getSplineOrderM();

Normals normals = new Normals(nUnknowns, width);

// *****
// the normal equations are accumulated here, followed by
// normals.reduceAndSolve() and updating of the unknowns.
// *****

// three vectors to hold the partial derivatives of the angles wrt the attitude parameters
FieldAngleCalculator fac = new FieldAngleCalculatorImpl();
GVectorNd vecAl = new GVectorNd(nUnknowns);
GVectorNd vecAcP = new GVectorNd(nUnknowns);
GVectorNd vecAcF = new GVectorNd(nUnknowns);

// the time at which the attitude uncertainty should be computed
long timeNs = 6311600000000000L;

// the left index, non-zero values of the B-splines and attitude quaternion
int left = ks.findLeft(timeNs);
double[] bSplineFunc = ks.bSplines(timeNs, left);
Quaternion q = new Quaternion(spline.value(timeNs).toArray()).normalize();

// set a proper direction for the preceding FoV center (eta=0, zeta=0, f=1)
GVector3d prpDirP = fac.getProperDir(0.0, 0.0, 1.0, q);
double[] dEtaDq = fac.computeDetaDq();
double[] dZetaDqP = fac.computeDzetaDq();

// set a proper direction for the following FoV center (eta=0, zeta=0, f=-1)
GVector3d prpDirF = fac.getProperDir(0.0, 0.0, -1.0, q);
double[] dZetaDqF = fac.computeDzetaDq();

// fill in the vectors of partial derivatives w.r.t. attitude parameters
int k = left * Quaternion.NUM_COMP;
for (int i = 0; i < splineOrder; i++) {
    for (int j = 0; j < Quaternion.NUM_COMP; j++) {
        vecAl.set(k, bSplineFunc[i] * dEtaDq[j]);
        vecAcP.set(k, bSplineFunc[i] * dZetaDqP[j]);
        vecAcF.set(k, bSplineFunc[i] * dZetaDqF[j]);
        k++;
    }
}

// reduce the vectors, i.e., pre-multiply by the inverse of the transposed Cholesky factor
vecAl = normals.reduceVector(vecAl);
vecAcP = normals.reduceVector(vecAcP);
vecAcF = normals.reduceVector(vecAcF);

// compute the uncertainties (sigma) and correlation coefficients (rho)
double sigmaAl = vecAl.norm();
double sigmaAcP = vecAcP.norm();
double sigmaAcF = vecAcF.norm();
double rhoAlAcP = vecAl.dot(vecAcP) / (sigmaAl * sigmaAcP);
double rhoAlAcF = vecAl.dot(vecAcF) / (sigmaAl * sigmaAcF);
double rhoAcPAcF = vecAcP.dot(vecAcF) / (sigmaAcP * sigmaAcF);
    
```

B Appendix: Efficient computation of Eqs. (9)–(10)

For a band matrix of dimension n and (half-)bandwidth b ($= 1 + \max(i - j)$, where i and j are the row and column indices of a non-zero element), the number of floating-point operations (flops) in each step of Cholesky algorithm, Eq. (12), is approximately given by:

- for C1 (Cholesky factorization of the matrix): $O_1 = nb(b + 1)/2$ flops and n square roots,
- for C2 (reduce the right-hand side): $O_2 = n(b + 1)$ flops,
- for C3 (solve the right-hand side): $O_3 = n(b + 1)$ flops,

assuming that $b \ll n$ (Björck, 1996). Here, one ‘flop’ roughly corresponds to one multiplication, one addition, and some subscripting.

In terms of N , the number of degrees of freedom of the spline, and assuming cubic splines ($M = 4$), we have $n = QN = 4N$ and $w = QM = 16$, where $Q = 4$ is the number of components of the quaternion, so $O_1 = 544N$ and $O_2 = 68N$. However, if C2 is to be done 6 times per knot interval (viz., in three components AL, ACP, ACF and at two times per knot interval), that is a total of $6N$ times, the total number of flops for calculating the attitude variances will be of the order of $408N^2$, or roughly a factor N longer than the Cholesky factorization. This is clearly unacceptable unless N is a rather small value (recall $N \simeq 1.6 \times 10^7$ for the whole mission). A solution could be to segment the attitude estimation, as is in fact done for the attitude update, but it would have to use really short segments, which is undesirable and inelegant.

A much more attractive possibility is based on the observation that the vectors \mathbf{d} and \mathbf{h} in Eqs. (9)–(10) need not use the full length $n = QN$ of the right-hand side. Indeed, if the quantity s only involves the attitude at a single point, with left index ℓ , both vectors are strictly zero for index $< Q\ell$, and \mathbf{d} is also strictly zero for index $\geq Q(\ell + M)$. (So \mathbf{d} only contains QM non-zero elements.) Moreover, the elements in \mathbf{h} decrease in absolute size rather rapidly for index greater than $\geq Q(\ell + M)$, in a similar way as the correlation goes away for separations of several knot intervals in Fig. 1, or the ‘influence function’ shown by the bottom diagram of Fig. 2 in Lindegren (LL-070). Thus, the calculation of \mathbf{h} in Eq. (9) and summing of $\mathbf{h}'\mathbf{h}$ in Eq. (10) can be restricted to the index range from $Q\ell$ to $Q(\ell + LM)$, where L is some smallish number (of the order of 12; cf. Lindegren, LL-070). With this modification the total number of flops to calculate $6N$ attitude variances is reduced by the factor $2L/N$ to about $816NL$ or about 20 times the number of flops for the Cholesky factorization. Since this is only done once, after the convergence of AGIS, this number appears to be quite acceptable.

The calculation of covariances $\text{Cov}(s_1 s_2) = \mathbf{h}'_1 \mathbf{h}_2$ can be organized according to the same principle, only extending the index range for the calculations accordingly.

The `Normals` class already has the method `GVectorNd reduceVector(GVectorNd vectorIn)` which performs the transformation C2 on the vector given as argument, and re-

turns the transformed (reduced) vector. However, this is not very suitable for the present calculations. Special methods are needed to handle efficiently right-hand-sides that are only non-zero in a limited index range, including methods to calculate their scalar products.

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